

Advances in instance segmentation: Technologies, metrics and applications in computer vision

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ABSTRACT

Instance segmentation is an advanced technique in computer vision that focuses on identifying and classifying each individual object in an image at the pixel level. Unlike semantic segmentation, which groups pixels of similar objects without distinguishing between different instances, instance segmentation assigns unique labels to each object, even if they are of the same class. This makes it possible not only to detect the presence and category of objects in an image but also to locate each specific instance and clearly distinguish them from each other. This problem not only advances the technical and theoretical understanding of how machines see and process digital images, but also has a direct impact on various industries and sectors where computer vision is an essential part of the system. In this paper, we present the current deep learning-based technologies, the metrics used for their evaluation, and a review of general and concrete datasets in general and drone-specific contexts. The results of this study provide a compendium of easily deployable deep learning-based technologies. This review paper aims to accelerate the process of understanding and using instance segmentation technologies for the reader.

1. Introduction

Instance segmentation is an area of research in computer vision, particularly in applications that require a detailed and accurate understanding of visual content in images and videos. Located at the intersection of object detection and semantic segmentation, this field seeks not only to identify the objects present in an image, but also to precisely delineate each instance, thus providing a level of detail and understanding of the composition of visual scenes.

Image segmentation can be defined as "the process of dividing a digital image into several segments that may contain significant information, thus facilitating its analysis" [1–3]. This process encompasses identifying Regions of Interest (ROIs), which may be highlighted by contours, bounding boxes, and masks, among other markers.

Identification of ROIs is facilitated through detection technologies. Object detection, a fundamental challenge within computer vision systems, involves locating and classifying objects. Y. Xiao et al. [4] describe it as "the essence of object detection is to locate and classify objects, for which rectangular bounding boxes are used to locate detected objects and classify object categories". This field is intertwined with classification, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation. Image

classification labels an image from a set of possible classes. Meanwhile, object detection assigns categories at the level of bounding boxes within the image. Semantic and instance segmentation go further, classifying at the pixel level through masks. Moreover, instance segmentation has the ability to differentiate between multiple objects of the same class. Semantic segmentation has been extensively studied in recent years due to its outstanding application in the field of autonomous driving and especially in technologies with Artificial Neural Networks (ANN). However, these technologies present difficulties in differentiating objects of the same class, especially when objects are closely related in the images [5].

For instance, in an image featuring two people, semantic segmentation would identify both as persons, whereas instance segmentation would label them as person 1 and person 2, as illustrated in Fig. 1.

While detection, segmentation and semantic segmentation are closely related, the fine details that differentiate each of these problems make them completely different from each other in terms of their formulation, but object detection is the basis for instance segmentation.

Image instance segmentation is the previous step of video instance segmentation. This involves extending image segmentation to the time domain. According to L. Yang et al. [7] "Video instance segmentation is

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more difficult than image instance segmentation, as it requires not only segmentation of instances into individual frames, but also tracking of instances between frames".

Although working with ROIs, defined by bounding boxes (bboxes), simplifies the tracking problem considerably, working with masks requires major additional challenges.

Instance segmentation is based on object detection methods, which are essential to identify the locations and categories of objects within an image. Object detectors are algorithms or models designed to identify and locate objects in a visual scene by predicting boundaries and classifying objects into categories. These detectors serve as the foundation for instance segmentation tasks by generating initial object proposals or bounding boxes, which are further refined into pixel-level segmentations. In other words, an instance segmentation model can be considered as an object detector extending its definition to the pixel-level.

Although video instance segmentation is beyond the scope of this paper, given its close relationship with instance segmentation, mention that current tendencies address the video instance segmentation problem with the brute force of deep learning. Works such as L. Yang et al. [7], S. Hao et al. [8], or P. Sun et al. [9] address the joint video object segmentation (VOS) problem and propose public datasets that include people under different conditions. In this context, we find in the literature three main trends:

- Automatic Video Object Segmentation (AVOS), which does not require user intervention.
- Semi-supervised Video Object Segmentation (SVOS) where the models receive information from the objects to be segmented. This type of segmentation has the advantage of being able to determine which objects are to be tracked. In this context, the work presented by H. K. Cheng and A. G. Schwing [10] has shown outstanding results for long-term video segmentation with respect to the state of the art.
- Interactive Video Object Segmentation (IVOS): In supervised segmentation, also called interactive, the model incorporates information from the user throughout the segmentation to produce a result, objects are selected at the beginning, and in an interactive process the result is shaped until the goal is achieved.

The applications of the instance segmentation is very varied and is applied in the study of cancer [11–13], astronomy [14,15], industries [16–20], recycling [21–23], infrastructures [24–27], autonomous driving [28–30], unmanned aerial vehicles [31,32], sustainable fishing [33], military [34,35], forestry studies [36,37], agriculture or precision livestock farming [32] and wildlife conservation [38] among others [39–44].

All previous applications face, to a greater or lesser extent, common challenges such as viewpoint variations, occlusions, lighting conditions, textured backgrounds, or shape variety, among others. Therefore, detectors must be able to recognize objects considering these difficulties, i. e., be invariant to these challenges. In addition, small object image instance segmentation, instance segmentation edge contour optimization, speed, continue to be studied.

There are specific datasets that directly address some of these challenges. This is achieved by grouping samples of the specific cases of each challenge in the datasets. One such dataset is the Occluded Video

Instance Segmentation (OVIS) challenge set [45]. This dataset includes instances with different levels of occlusion as measured by the Bounding-box Occlusion Rate (BOR). This metric helps models evaluate performance in scenarios where occlusion is prevalent, addressing one of the main challenges of video segmentation.

Throughout this paper we describe state-of-the-art methods, evaluation metrics, and datasets in the field of instance segmentation. This paper has been organized as follows. Section 2 details the various instance segmentation methods, including two-stage, single-stage, and multi-stage approaches, along with specific models and techniques within each category. Section 3 discusses the evaluation metrics used to assess instance segmentation models Section 4 reviews key datasets used for instance segmentation, categorized into generalist datasets, urban or autonomous driving datasets, and datasets specific to drones and aerial imagery. Finally, the discussion and conclusions are presented in Section 5.

2. Instance segmentation methods

The different paradigms of machine learning have addressed and continue to address the instance segmentation issue. Thus, the reader can find in State of the Art (SOTA) four main branches: supervised learning, unsupervised learning, semi-supervised learning, and reinforcement learning. Each paradigm has its own challenges. For example, supervised learning requires large labeled datasets that can be costly and time consuming to generate, creating a major bottleneck to scalability. Unsupervised learning, on the other hand, struggles to achieve high accuracy because models must infer patterns and structures without labeled data, often leading to less accurate results. Semi-supervised learning seeks a middle ground, but faces the challenge of effectively leveraging a small labeled dataset with a much larger unlabeled dataset, requiring sophisticated mechanisms to avoid bias. Finally, reinforcement learning often faces difficulties in defining appropriate reward functions and managing computational complexity, which can hinder its applicability to real-world scenarios. In this paper, we focus on supervised learning methods, as they have shown the most consistent success in the field of instance segmentation.

Previous review [5,46] shows the classification of instance segmentation methods according to different criteria. In Fig. 2 we show a diagram of the general taxonomy of instance segmentation based on supervised learning, inspired by previous review work.

Fully supervised instance segmentation methods can be categorized on the basis of the number of stages they involve. These categories include one-stage, two-stage, and multi-stage methods. Traditionally, two-stage instance segmentation methods have predominated, using object detection results to inform segmentation tasks. These methods can be divided into top-down and bottom-up approaches. Top-down methods start with object detection, creating bounding boxes within which segmentation is performed. Bottom-up methods, on the other hand, begin by mapping pixels into high-dimensional space and then grouping them into instances using clustering techniques. Although two-stage methods have been successful, their performance is heavily dependent on the quality of the initial object detection or pixel mapping.

Single-stage methods have been developed to address some of the limitations of two-stage methods. These methods perform detection and

Fig. 1. Difference between a) detection, b) semantic segmentation, and c) instance segmentation. (Image with Id=24 of the COCO [6] database).

Fig. 2. General taxonomy for instance segmentation with a focus on supervised learning [5,46].

segmentation in a single pass, reducing inference time and potentially improving efficiency by allowing simultaneous learning of detection and segmentation tasks [47].

Multi-stage methods further refine instance segmentation by incrementally improving predictions at each stage. This approach exploits mutual information between stages to improve segmentation accuracy.

The order of presentation of the approaches in this section begins with single-stage methods, followed by two-stage methods, and finally multistage methods.

2.1. Single-stage methods

Single-stage instance segmentation methods streamline the segmentation process by performing detection and segmentation in a single pass. These methods emphasize efficiency and speed, making them ideal for real-time applications. Single-stage approaches can be broadly categorized into anchor-based and anchor-free methods.

Anchor-based methods use predefined anchor boxes to predict the positions and segmentations of objects. These methods often use sliding-window techniques and linear combinations to generate object masks. The sliding window approach ensures comprehensive coverage of the image by applying fixed-size windows over different regions, predicting object masks at different scales and locations. This method takes advantage of multi-scale features and integrates detection and segmentation into a unified framework. On the other hand, linear combination methods improve anchor-based segmentation by splitting the task into generating prototype masks and predicting per-instance mask coefficients. This approach achieves high efficiency by linearly combining the prototypes with the mask coefficients, thus eliminating the need for feature re-pooling and significantly improving segmentation speed.

Anchor-free methods eschew predefined anchors and instead rely on keypoints or direct mask prediction techniques to segment objects. These methods often extend existing recognition frameworks and employ innovative techniques such as feature embedding and localization-based segmentation. Anchor-free approaches offer flexibility and simplicity because they do not require predefined anchor configurations and can predict object masks directly from image features. Within anchor-free methods, fully convolutional one-stage object detector (FCOS) extension methods adapt the FCOS framework for instance segmentation by introducing additional branches to predict instance masks. These branches often incorporate spatial attention

mechanisms to improve mask accuracy and segmentation quality. Segmentation by object localization methods decouple mask generation into mask kernel prediction and mask feature learning, enabling efficient and high-resolution mask generation. They often introduce innovative non-maximum suppression techniques to improve performance and reduce inference overhead. In Table 1 we show the principal single-stage methods.

2.1.1. Anchor-based methods

Anchor-based methods in single-level instance segmentation rely on predefined anchor boxes to detect and segment objects. These methods often use sliding-window techniques to generate instance masks for objects at different scales and locations, and linear combination to improve single-stage anchor-based segmentation by splitting the task into generating prototype masks and predicting per-instance mask coefficients. They combine detection and segmentation tasks into a single mesh and optimize both simultaneously for efficiency.

Sliding-window approaches in anchor-based methods apply a fixed-size window across the image to predict object masks. This method ensures comprehensive coverage of the image, allowing detection and segmentation of objects at different scales and locations. It takes advantage of multiscale features and integrates detection and segmentation into a unified framework. The main models are described below.

Mask SSD [48] is a single-stage approach to object instance segmentation that builds on the SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) framework. It integrates a detection subnetwork to predict object categories and location of bounding boxes with an instance-level segmentation subnetwork to generate foreground masks for each instance. The model leverages multi-scale and feedback features from different convolutional layers to represent objects of various sizes more accurately. In addition, an assistant classification network guides the prediction of the class score by dividing the classification into objectness prior and likelihood of categories. Mask SSD uses a multi-task loss function to jointly optimize detection and segmentation, allowing for direct prediction of both outputs.

The Instance-Sensitive Fully Convolutional Network (InstanceFCN) [49] extends the traditional Fully Convolutional Network (FCN) for instance segmentation by computing instance-sensitive score maps instead of a generic score map. Each pixel in these score maps classifies its relative position to an object instance, allowing object segments to be generated directly from these maps. The architecture features a fully convolutional branch for estimating segment instances and another for scoring these instances. Instance-sensitive score maps are generated by transforming feature maps through convolutional layers and assembling instances through a sliding-window approach. InstanceFCN exploits local image coherence to efficiently generate instance segments, avoiding the need for high-dimensional layers dependent on mask resolution.

TensorMask [50] is a framework for dense sliding window instance segmentation that treats instance segmentation as a prediction task over 4D tensors. Unlike traditional methods that use bounding boxes followed by segmentation, TensorMask predicts dense sliding window masks directly. The architecture uses structured 4D tensors to represent masks over a spatial domain, where both (H, W) represent the object position and (V, U) the relative mask position. TensorMask uses a pyramid structure called a tensor bipyramid, which captures the property

Table 1
Single-stage methods.

Principal Branche	Sub Branche	Reference
Anchor-Based Methods	Sliding Window	[48–50]
	Linear Combination	[51–53]
Anchor-Free Methods	FCOS Extension	[54,55]
	Segment Object by Localization	[56–61]

that large objects have high-resolution masks with coarse spatial localization, while small objects have low-resolution masks with fine spatial localization. This framework results in masks that are class agnostic and predicted directly from feature maps.

Linear combination methods improve single-stage anchor-based segmentation by splitting the task into generating prototype masks and predicting per-instance mask coefficients. These methods achieve high efficiency by linearly combining the prototypes with the mask coefficients, eliminating the need for feature re-pooling and significantly improving segmentation speed. The main models are described below.

YOLOACT++ [52] improves on YOLOACT [51] by introducing a real-time instance segmentation model that splits the task into two parallel subtasks: generating a set of prototype masks and predicting per-instance mask coefficients. This method achieves high efficiency and quality by linearly combining the prototypes with the mask coefficients, avoiding the need for feature re-pooling. YOLOACT++ incorporates several enhancements, including deformable convolutions for better feature sampling, optimized prediction heads with better anchor scales and aspect ratios, and a novel fast mask re-scoring branch to correlate classification confidence with mask quality. The architecture uses a fully convolutional network based on ResNet-101 with Feature Pyramid Network (FPN) and employs fast Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) to further increase speed without significant performance penalty.

Sparse Instance Activation for Real-Time Instance Segmentation (SparseIns) [53] introduces a novel, efficient, fully convolutional framework for real-time instance segmentation by using a sparse set of instance activation maps (IAMs) to highlight informative regions for each foreground object. These maps allow for the aggregation of instance-level features directly from the highlighted regions for detection and segmentation. The architecture consists of a backbone network for feature extraction, an encoder to enhance multi-scale representations, and a decoder to compute instance activation maps and perform instance recognition and segmentation. SparseIns uses bipartite matching to predict objects in a one-to-one style, avoiding non-maximum suppression (NMS) in post-processing.

2.1.2. Anchor-free methods

Anchor-free methods bypass the need for predefined anchor boxes and instead rely on techniques such as keypoint detection and direct mask prediction. These methods offer greater flexibility and simplicity, allowing masks to be generated directly from image features without the constraints of predefined anchor configurations. This branch can be split into a fully convolutional one-stage object detector (FCOS) extension and a segment object by localization.

FCOS extension methods adapt the FCOS framework for instance segmentation. These methods introduce additional branches to predict instance masks, often incorporating spatial attention mechanisms to improve mask accuracy and segmentation quality. The main models are described below.

CenterMask [54] introduces an efficient anchor-free instance segmentation model by adding a spatial attention-guided mask (SAG-Mask) branch to the single-stage anchor-free FCOS detector. This SAG-Mask branch focuses on informative pixels while suppressing noise, thereby improving mask prediction accuracy. The model uses an enhanced backbone network, VoVNetV2, with residual connections and an effective squeeze excitation (eSE) module for improved performance and speed.

EmbedMask [55] is a one-stage instance segmentation method that combines the strengths of proposal-based and segmentation-based methods. Based on the FCOS detection model, EmbedMask introduces pixel embedding and proposal embedding to perform efficient pixel clustering. Pixel embedding provides a representation for each pixel, while proposal embedding represents the instance proposals. The model predicts masks by coupling these embeddings, assigning pixels to instance proposals based on embedding similarity. This approach avoids the complexity of re-pooling operations, preserves image detail, and

enables the generation of high-resolution masks.

Segmenting objects by localization methods decouple mask generation into mask kernel prediction and mask feature learning. These approaches dynamically predict convolution kernels for instance-aware segmentation, enabling efficient and high-resolution mask generation. They often introduce innovative non-maximum suppression techniques to improve performance and reduce inference overhead. The main models are described below.

SOLOv2 [57] extends the original SOLO [56] framework by introducing a fast and dynamic instance segmentation solution. It employs a dynamic mask representation scheme that decouples mask generation into mask kernel prediction and mask feature learning, enabling efficient and high-resolution instance segmentation. The model dynamically predicts input-dependent convolution kernels, which are then applied to unified mask features for instance-aware segmentation. In addition, SOLOv2 introduces Matrix NMS, a novel non-maximum suppression technique that performs NMS with parallel matrix operations, significantly reducing inference overhead.

PaFPN-SOLO [58] is an algorithm that improves the SOLOv2 model by introducing a Path Aggregation Feature Pyramid Network (PaFPN) and non-local operations to improve the accuracy of feature extraction and localization. The PaFPN network addresses the problem of long propagation paths of low-level position information by implementing bottom-up path augmentation, which extracts more accurate position information from lower feature layers. Additionally, non-local operations are added to the ResNet backbone to capture long-range dependencies and preserve feature information during the feature extraction process. These modifications result in improved segmentation accuracy and efficiency.

Boundary-Aware One-Stage Instance Segmentation (BSOLO) [59] extends the SOLO framework by incorporating boundary refinement to improve mask accuracy. The core innovation is a Hungarian algorithm-based boundary loss that calculates the matching cost between boundaries, effectively measuring boundary differences, and contributing to the generation of high-quality instance masks. BSOLO introduces two additional modules: the Feature Fusion Network (FFN) and the Prototype Attention Module (PAM). The FFN captures long-range dependencies and fuses multi-scale features, while the PAM enhances mask assembly through channel attention. This approach ensures refined boundary information and precise instance masks.

VB-SOLO [60] extends the original SOLOv2 by integrating Efficient Channel Attention (ECA) and Bi-directional Feature Pyramid Network (BiFPN) for improved instance segmentation of overlapping epithelial cells. The model uses VoVNetv2 as its backbone, optimized with ECA to increase information interaction across channels. BiFPN is introduced to achieve weighted fusion of multi-scale features, preserving more shallow semantic information. In addition, a Convolutional Block Attention Module (CBAM) is added to the mask branch to improve focus on cell regions.

MP-PolarMask [61] improves the original PolarMask model by addressing its limitations in representing concave objects and inefficiencies in ray regression. The key innovation is the introduction of multiple Polar systems, extending from one main Polar system to four auxiliary Polar systems. This multi-point approach allows MP-PolarMask to better represent complex shapes by using additional rays from auxiliary centers located in different quadrants of the object. The architecture includes a backbone network for feature extraction, followed by the Multi-Point Head (MP-Head) that calculates the main and auxiliary centers along with their corresponding rays.

2.2. Two-stage methods

Two-stage instance segmentation methods involve a two-step process: first, generating region proposals to identify potential object locations, and second, refining these proposals to produce final segmentation masks. This method is divided into several approaches,

each of which uses different techniques to improve accuracy and efficiency. Within the two-step framework, there are two main approaches, Top-down and bottom-up instance segmentation.

First, Top-down instance segmentation approach starts with object detection, creating bounding boxes for potential objects, which are then refined into segmentation masks. This method relies heavily on the accuracy of the initial detection phase and is further subdivided into dense sliding window methods, multi-level feature methods, R-CNN variants, and contour information methods. Dense sliding window methods utilize a fixed-size window that moves across the image, predicting object masks at each location to ensure comprehensive coverage. Multi-level feature methods, on the other hand, combine activations from multiple convolutional network layers to generate masks, capturing both high-level semantic information and low-level spatial details. The R-CNN variants extend object detection frameworks by adding segmentation capabilities; proposals generated by the Region Proposal Network (RPN) are refined using a mask prediction network. Lastly, contour information methods focus on delineating object boundaries, integrating contour detection with segmentation frameworks to produce precise masks.

The second one, Bottom-up instance segmentation approach, starts by labeling each pixel in the image and then groups these pixels into distinct object instances. This method bypasses initial object detection and instead uses pixel-level information to form object boundaries. This method is highly flexible and can handle complex scenes with overlapping or occluded objects. It is further divided into object box cropping methods, contour information methods, pixel center prediction methods, depth information methods, and clustering methods. Object box cropping methods refine initial semantic segmentations into instance-level predictions using higher-order contextual information. Contour information methods use pixel-level predictions to define object boundaries, integrating contour detection with segmentation to form precise masks from the ground up. Pixel center prediction methods assign pixels to object instances based on predicted center points, clustering pixels into coherent masks. Depth information methods incorporate depth cues into segmentation, providing additional context to distinguish overlapping or closely spaced objects. Clustering methods group pixels into object instances by learning affinity scores or embeddings that indicate pixel similarity, often using graph-based algorithms to ensure that similar pixels form coherent object masks.

Throughout this subsection, we describe the main aspects of several two-stage methods and a set of subgroups into which we can categorize the most prominent models in SOTA. In Table 2 below, we show the models to be described.

2.2.1. Top-down instance segmentation

Within the top-down instance, segmentation models can be categorized into dense sliding windows, multi-level feature methods, R-CNN-based methods, and contour-based methods.

Dense sliding windows methods apply a fixed size window across the image and predict segmentation masks at each location. This approach ensures that the entire image is covered, making it possible to detect and segment objects even in densely populated scenes. It has two

primary branches: one for predicting the segmentation mask and the other for evaluating the presence of the object in the window. The main models are described below.

DeepMask [62] predicts a candidate mask on each spatial region using a sliding window. The DeepMask model introduces a novel approach to generating object proposals using a discriminative convolutional network that is jointly trained to output a class-agnostic segmentation mask and an objectness score. This architecture allows DeepMask to efficiently apply the model to the entire image at multiple scales during inference, producing a set of segmentation masks, each with a corresponding object likelihood score. This method consists of two main branches that emerge from common convolutional feature extraction layers, the Segmentation Branch and the Scoring Branch. The first branch predicts a segmentation mask for the object at the center of the input patch. This branch uses a single 1×1 convolution layer followed by a classification layer to determine whether each pixel belongs to the object. On the other hand, the scoring branch predicts the probability that an object is centered in the patch at the correct scale. This branch includes a 2×2 max-pooling layer followed by two fully connected layers to produce the final objectness score.

SharpMask [63] is an improved version of DeepMask that uses multi-scale features. SharpMask enhances the DeepMask model by integrating a top-down refinement approach to improve the quality of the segmentation mask. It combines spatial information from the lower layers with high-level features to produce detailed masks. Initially, a coarse mask is generated through a feedforward pathway, then refined using top-down modules that progressively increase resolution. SharpMask's architecture includes a feedforward pathway for coarse mask generation and top-down refinement modules for detailed enhancement. This approach produces sharper, more accurate masks that are better aligned with object boundaries, while improving run-time efficiency, resulting in a 50 % speed improvement over DeepMask.

Multi-level feature methods use activations from different layers of a convolutional network to generate instance masks. By integrating features from both the higher and lower layers of the network, these methods capture a rich representation of objects, combining semantic context with spatial precision. This results in better localization and more detailed object boundaries. The main models are described below.

The Hypercolumns [64] model uses features from multiple layers to predict instance masks. The Hypercolumns model introduces a new method for object segmentation and fine-grained localization by using activations from multiple layers of a convolutional network as pixel descriptors. Instead of relying solely on the final layer, which may be too coarse for precise localization, hypercolumns use both semantic information from the upper layers and spatial precision from the lower layers. The hypercolumn at a pixel is the concatenated vector of activations from all layers above that pixel. This method improves tasks such as simultaneous detection and segmentation, keypoint localization, and part labeling by providing a rich, multi-scale representation of each pixel. The architecture integrates feature maps at different resolutions through bilinear interpolation, allowing the model to maintain high resolution while capturing different features. Benefits include improved segmentation accuracy, better part localization, and improved keypoint prediction, as demonstrated by significant performance gains on various benchmarks.

The Path Aggregation Network (PANet) [65] introduces enhancements to the feature hierarchy in instance segmentation models by integrating bottom-up path augmentation and adaptive feature pooling. This architecture aims to improve information flow and localization by augmenting low-level features with accurate localization signals. The augmentation of the bottom-up path creates shorter paths between low-level and top-level features, improving the propagation of localization information. Adaptive feature pooling aggregates features from all levels for each proposal, ensuring comprehensive use of information. In addition, a fully connected fusion branch improves mask prediction by incorporating different views of each proposal. PANet achieves

Table 2

Two-stage methods.

Principal Branch	Sub-Branch	Reference
Top-down	Dense Sliding Window	[62,63]
	Multi-Level Features	[64,65]
	R-CNN	[66,67]
	Contour Information	[68–70]
Bottom-up	Object Box Cropping	[71–74]
	Contour Information	[75,76]
	Pixel Center Prediction	[77–80]
	Depth Information	[81,82]
	Clustering	[83–86]

state-of-the-art performance on several benchmarks, demonstrating its effectiveness in improving segmentation accuracy, robustness across scales, and better localization.

R-CNN-based methods extend traditional object detection by adding segmentation capabilities. The region proposal network (RPN) generates candidate boxes, which are then refined using a segmentation network to produce detailed masks. These methods benefit from the robust object detection capabilities of R-CNN architectures, ensuring high accuracy in both detection and segmentation tasks. The main models are described below.

Mask R-CNN [67] is an extension to instance segmentation of the Regions with CNN Features family of detectors known as R-CNN. The first R-CNN model [87] was a major revolution in the field of object detection in terms of accuracy. However, the latency of the system was its main limitation. Therefore, studies focused on speeding up this process, resulting in the Fast R-CNN model [88] and its evolution Faster R-CNN [89], which incorporates a Region Proposal Network (RPN) to further speed up the computation of regions of interest (RoI). The Mask R-CNN model extends Faster R-CNN by adding a branch for predicting segmentation masks at each RoI, in parallel with the existing branch for classification and bounding box regression. This architecture includes an RPN that proposes candidate bounding boxes for objects. In the second stage, the network extracts features from each candidate box using the RoIAlign layer, which preserves spatial alignment and improves mask accuracy. The mask branch, a small fully convolutional network (FCN), is applied to each RoI to predict a segmentation mask on a pixel-by-pixel basis. This approach decouples mask prediction from class prediction, allowing each class to have its binary mask without competition. Mask R-CNN achieves state-of-the-art results in instance segmentation, bounding-box object detection, and person keypoint detection, demonstrating its flexibility and efficiency.

Mask Scoring R-CNN [66] extends the Mask R-CNN [67] framework by introducing a MaskIoU head to learn the quality of predicted instance masks. This model addresses the mismatch between mask quality and classification scores that can degrade instance segmentation performance. The architecture consists of the standard Mask R-CNN structure with an additional MaskIoU head that takes both the instance feature and the predicted mask as input to regress the IoU between the predicted mask and its ground truth. The MaskIoU head includes four convolutional layers and three fully connected layers to output the MaskIoU score. During inference, the predicted MaskIoU is multiplied by the classification score to produce a final mask score that reflects both the semantic category and the completeness of the mask.

Contour-based methods focus on accurately delineating object boundaries by predicting contours. These methods integrate contour detection with segmentation frameworks, allowing for precise and detailed object masks. They are particularly useful for tasks that require fine-grained boundary delineation, such as medical imaging or detailed object recognition. The main models are described below.

MaskLab [68] builds on Faster R-CNN by introducing additional outputs for semantic segmentation and predicting the center direction of the instance to improve the segmentation of the instance. The model produces three outputs: refined box predictions, semantic segmentation logits, and direction prediction logits. These outputs allow MaskLab to distinguish between objects of different semantic classes and to separate instances of the same class by predicting the direction of each pixel towards its corresponding instance center. Semantic segmentation logits are used to predict pixel-wise semantic labels, while direction prediction logits are used to determine the direction of each pixel relative to the center of the object. The architecture incorporates hypercolumn features for mask refinement and atrous convolution for extracting denser feature maps.

The Explicit Shape Encoding (ESE) model [69] introduces a novel instance segmentation framework that significantly reduces computational load by explicitly encoding object shapes into short vectors. The key innovation is the use of a contour-based shape signature, named

Inner-center Radius (IR), which converts object contours into polar coordinates with respect to an inner-center point. This signature is then approximated using Chebyshev polynomials to create a compact and robust shape vector. The ESE model employs modern object detectors to predict both the bounding box and the shape vector, allowing simultaneous decoding of multiple object shapes using simple tensor operations.

The DeepSnakes [70] model is a model that combines deep learning with the traditional active contour model (snakes) [90] for instance segmentation. The model leverages a CNN backbone to provide initial object detection and contour points, which are then iteratively refined using a snake-based optimization process. This integration allows DeepSnakes to accurately capture object boundaries by evolving the initial contour points to fit the exact shape of the object. The architecture consists of an initial detection network to predict coarse contour points, followed by an active contour refinement process that optimizes these points based on image gradients and object boundaries. This dual approach allows DeepSnakes to achieve high segmentation accuracy and robust performance on various benchmarks.

2.2.2. Bottom-up instance segmentation

Within the top-down instance segmentation models can be categorized into object box cropping, bottom-up contour-based approaches, pixel center prediction methods, depth-information methods, and clustering-based methods.

Object box cropping methods refine initial semantic segmentations into instance-level predictions using higher-order contextual information. Techniques such as Conditional Random Fields (CRFs) are used to improve pixel-level segmentations, allowing accurate separation of individual object instances within a given category. The main models are described below.

The Deep Conditional Random Fields (DeepCRFs) [71] model integrates deep learning with higher-order conditional random fields (CRFs) to achieve accurate bottom-up instance segmentation. The model starts with category-level semantic segmentation using a deep neural network, and then uses a CRF to refine this segmentation into instance-level predictions. The CRF incorporates higher-order potentials based on object detector outputs, allowing the model to reason about object instances from the initial semantic segmentation. This approach leverages the strengths of semantic segmentation and object detection to produce accurate instance segmentations. The model is fully differentiable, allowing end-to-end training.

The Dynamically Instantiated Network (DIN) model [72] integrates semantic segmentation and instance segmentation by dynamically creating instance segmentation subnetworks based on the output of an initial semantic segmentation module. This architecture starts with a semantic segmentation network that provides a category-level segmentation map. An instance subnetwork is then dynamically instantiated for each detected object, using the initial semantic segmentation and object detection outputs to distinguish between different instances. The instance subnetwork uses a Conditional Random Field (CRF) model to refine segmentations by combining information from the object detector and the semantic segmentation output. This approach allows DIN to produce accurate per-instance segmentations without the need for post-processing steps. The fully differentiable network is trained end-to-end, leveraging the robustness of semantic segmentation to handle errors in object detection and occlusions between objects.

The PolarMask++ model [74] extends the original PolarMask [73] by improving the polar representation for single-shot instance segmentation. It reformulates the instance segmentation task into a contour prediction problem in polar coordinates, where the shape of an object is represented by rays emitted from the center to the object boundary at different angles. This anchor-box-free and single-shot framework integrates two key modules: soft polar centering and polar Intersection over Union (IoU) loss, which improve the sampling of high-quality center examples and optimize contour regression. PolarMask++ introduces a refined feature pyramid to further improve feature

representation across scales, allowing for more accurate instance segmentation. PolarMask++ unifies instance segmentation and object detection, reducing computational complexity and eliminating dependence on bounding box predictions, resulting in a faster and more efficient training process.

Bottom-up contour-based approaches use pixel-level predictions to define object boundaries, integrating contour detection with segmentation to build accurate masks from the ground up. By focusing on edges, these methods effectively segment instances without relying on initial bounding-box predictions. The main models are described below.

The Deep Watershed Transform (DWT) [75] model integrates the classical watershed transform with modern deep learning techniques to achieve instance segmentation. This approach involves predicting an energy map of the input image where each object instance is represented as a distinct energy basin. The model begins with a semantic segmentation step using a deep neural network to focus on relevant areas. The output is then refined through a Direction Network (DN) that predicts the direction of descent for the energy landscape, followed by a Watershed Transform Network (WTN) that generates a discretized watershed energy map. The final segmentation is obtained by cutting a single energy level to yield connected components corresponding to object instances. This method is efficient, avoiding over-segmentation and achieving high accuracy with fast inference times.

The BoundaryFormer [76] introduces an end-to-end instance segmentation method that regresses polygonal boundaries for each object instance using a transformer-based architecture. This model predicts the boundaries as polygons while using instance mask segmentations for supervision through a novel differentiable grid module. The architecture starts with a standard feature pyramid network (FPN) and proposes object bounding boxes that initialize ellipsoidal polygons. These polygons are iteratively refined by attention mechanisms that allow point-to-point and point-to-feature interactions. This process produces high-resolution polygons as the refinement progresses. The polygonal representation of the model facilitates accurate boundary delineation, which is beneficial for several downstream tasks.

Pixel center prediction methods assign pixels to object instances based on predicted centers. Each pixel is associated with an object center, clustering pixels into coherent masks. This method reduces complexity and improves segmentation speed by directly associating pixels with object centers. The main models are described below.

The Box2Pix model [77] proposes a single-shot approach to instance segmentation by assigning pixels to object boxes. It relies on a single fully convolutional network (FCN) to predict object bounding boxes, pixel-wise semantic classes, and offset vectors pointing to the corresponding object centers. The network architecture combines the efficiency of GoogLeNet-v1 style with SSD (Single Shot MultiBox Detector) for real-time performance. The FCN predicts bounding boxes, semantic segmentation, and center-offset vectors in a single forward pass. A post-processing step assigns each pixel to the best matching object detection based on the predicted offset vectors, ensuring accurate instance segmentation at real-time speeds.

The Spatial Embeddings model [78] proposes a new clustering loss function for proposal-free instance segmentation that optimizes the spatial embeddings of pixels and jointly learns an instance-specific clustering bandwidth. Each pixel is associated with an object by learning an offset vector pointing to the object's center. The network predicts spatial embeddings and clustering bandwidth, ensuring that pixels belonging to the same object are close together in the embedding space while being sufficiently separated from other objects. This method enables real-time performance while maintaining high segmentation accuracy. Evaluated on the Cityscapes benchmark, Spatial Embeddings achieves top results, outperforming Mask R-CNN with an average precision of 27.6 and operating at more than 10 fps on 2MP images.

Conditional Convolutions for Instance Segmentation (CondInst) model [79] introduces a dynamic approach to instance segmentation using instance-aware networks. Unlike traditional methods such as Mask

R-CNN, which rely on ROI operations, CondInst uses a fully convolutional network where the mask head is conditioned on instances. This method eliminates the need for ROI clipping and feature alignment. CondInst dynamically generates convolutional filters for each instance, allowing the mask head to be very compact and efficient. The network predicts instance masks directly from the feature maps, guided by instance-specific parameters generated by a controller network. The architecture consists of an instance-aware mask head applied to feature maps, with filters dynamically generated for each instance, reducing computational complexity and improving performance.

ExtremeNet [80] introduces a bottom-up object detection framework that predicts four extreme points (top, left, bottom, right) and a center point for each object using a keypoint estimation network. These keypoints are grouped into bounding boxes when they are geometrically aligned, transforming object detection into an appearance-based keypoint estimation problem. The network uses a state-of-the-art keypoint estimation framework to generate heat maps for each extreme point and the center of the object. It then uses a geometric approach to group these keypoints, forming bounding boxes when the center point aligns with the geometric center of the extreme points. This method not only achieves competitive performance with region-based detection methods, but also produces coarse octagonal masks directly from the extreme points. Key innovations include a purely geometric grouping mechanism and the use of extreme points for fine-grained mask prediction.

Depth-information methods incorporate depth cues into segmentation, providing additional context for distinguishing overlapping or closely spaced objects. Integrating depth data with pixel-level segmentation improves the accuracy of the boundary and the understanding of spatial arrangement. The main models are described below.

Pixel-level Encoding and Depth Layering (PEDL) [81] improves instance-level semantic labeling by combining fully convolutional networks (FCNs) with depth information and pixel-level coding. The network predicts three outputs: semantic labels, depth, and direction to instance centers. Semantic labels provide pixel-level classification, while depth information aids in object scaling and separation. The direction output encodes the angle from each pixel to its corresponding instance center, facilitating boundary detection and instance separation. This combination allows robust and accurate instance segmentation, which is particularly effective in urban street scenes.

The Monocular model [82] approaches instance-level segmentation and depth ordering from a single monocular image using convolutional neural networks (CNNs). The approach combines predictions from CNNs applied to overlapping patches of different resolutions and integrates these predictions with a Markov Random Field (MRF) to produce coherent instance-level segmentation and depth ordering. Each instance ID encodes depth information, allowing the model not only to segment objects but also to determine their relative distances from the camera. The network is trained to predict depth-ordered instance segmentations directly from image patches, using 3D bounding box annotations and stereo images during training.

Clustering-based methods group pixels into object instances by learning affinity scores or embeddings that indicate pixel similarity. Graph-based algorithms are often used to cluster pixels, ensuring that similar pixels form coherent object masks. These methods are effective for segmenting amorphous or irregularly shaped objects, where traditional bounding-box methods may struggle. The main models are described below.

The Affinity Derivation and Graph Merge (ADGM) [83] model introduces a suggestion-free instance segmentation scheme based on pixel affinity information, which determines the relationship between pixels belonging to the same instance. The architecture uses two neural networks: one to predict pixel-level semantic scores and the other to infer pixel affinities. The affinity information is used to construct a graph, where pixels are treated as vertices and affinities as edges. A graph merging algorithm then clusters pixels into instances. This approach effectively combines semantic segmentation with pixel affinity to

generate fine-grained instance masks.

The Single-Shot Affinity Pyramid (SSAP) model [84] proposes a proposal-free instance segmentation approach that operates with a single forward pass. The model jointly learns a pixel-level semantic segmentation and an affinity pyramid that predict the probability that pixel pairs belong to the same instance. The SSAP framework uses a U-shaped network to generate multi-scale affinity pyramids and semantic labels, exploiting both short- and long-range affinities. The Cascaded Graph Partition (CGP) module is then used to progressively refine instance predictions from coarse to fine scales based on the learned affinities. SSAP demonstrates high accuracy and efficiency by requiring only a single pass for instance segmentation. This model effectively captures detailed structures in finely annotated images and outperforms several existing methods in terms of average accuracy and panoptic quality metrics.

The Recurrent Pixel Embedding (RPE) [85] introduces an end-to-end trainable framework for pixel-level grouping tasks such as instance segmentation. It regresses pixels into a hyperspherical embedding space where pixels of the same group have high cosine similarity. The model uses a novel recurrent mean-shift clustering implemented as a recurrent neural network to group pixels into instances, providing a probabilistic interpretation of the instance grouping. The network consists of two components: a pixel embedding network that projects pixels into the embedding space, and a recurrent grouping module that iteratively refines pixel embeddings.

ClusterNet [86] is designed for 3D instance segmentation in RGB-D images, which is critical for autonomous robots to understand complex scenes. It avoids region proposals by predicting first- and second-order moments of object occupancy functions, allowing regression of object location, size, and pose directly from pixel predictions. The model uses an hourglass deep neural network (DNN) in which each pixel votes for the 3D position of its corresponding object center. Final instance segmentation is achieved by clustering in the space of these moments, followed by a refinement step using a Gaussian Mixture Model (GMM).

2.3. Multi-stage methods

Multi-stage instance segmentation methods progressively refine predictions through multiple stages. Each stage builds on the results of the previous one, allowing for more detailed and accurate segmentation results. These methods are particularly effective in scenarios where high accuracy is required, as the multi-stage approach allows the model to iteratively improve its predictions. Multi-stage methods are generally classified into cascade architectures, RNN-based methods, and self-learning mechanisms.

Cascade architectures involve a series of stages in which both detection and segmentation are iteratively refined. This approach typically starts with bounding box regression and mask prediction, which are progressively improved at each stage. Cascade architectures are designed to improve the quality of proposals and segmentation masks by using higher IoU thresholds at each stage, reducing overfitting and improving the accuracy of difficult segmentation tasks.

RNN-based methods use recurrent neural networks to segment instances one at a time. These methods use the sequential nature of RNNs to focus on one object at a time, often using attention mechanisms to handle occlusions and improve segmentation accuracy. By iteratively processing each instance, RNN-based methods can naturally handle variable-length outputs and provide detailed segmentation masks.

Self-attention mechanisms use transformers to refine query boxes and mask predictions. These methods benefit from the ability of transformers to handle long-range dependencies and focus on the relevant parts of the image, improving both detection and segmentation performance. Self-attention mechanisms are particularly effective in scenarios that require detailed and context-aware segmentation.

Table 3 shows a summary of the methods categorized in this branch.

Table 3
Multi-stage methods.

Branche	Reference
Cascade Architecture	[91,92]
RNN-Based Methods	[93,94]
Self-Attention Mechanisms	[95–97]

2.3.1. Cascade architecture

Cascade architecture methods integrate a series of stages where detection and segmentation functions are interleaved for joint multi-stage processing. Each stage improves the accuracy of both the bounding-box regression and mask prediction. By progressively refining the predictions at each stage, cascade architectures improve the quality of segmentation masks and effectively handle complex and difficult segmentation tasks. The main models are described below.

Hybrid Task Cascade (HTC) [91] integrates cascade architecture into instance segmentation by interleaving detection and segmentation functions for joint multi-stage processing. The model features progressive refinement through a cascaded pipeline that combines both bounding box regression and mask prediction at each stage. HTC incorporates a fully convolutional branch for semantic segmentation, which provides spatial context to enhance instance discrimination. The mask features of each stage are embedded and fed to the next stage, reinforcing the flow of information. This approach allows HTC to use contextual information from both foreground instances and background regions, resulting in more accurate predictions.

The Cascade Mask R-CNN [92] model extends the Cascade R-CNN framework to instance segmentation by adding a mask head to each detection stage. The architecture integrates cascaded bounding-box regression and cascaded mask prediction and iteratively refines both bounding boxes and masks. Each stage of the Cascade Mask R-CNN improves the quality of proposals and the accuracy of instance segmentation by sequentially training with higher Intersection over Union (IoU) thresholds. This multi-stage approach enables the model to handle more difficult segmentation tasks by refining the instances at each stage. The architecture is effective in reducing overfitting and improving high-quality detections by using the cascading stages to progressively refine the predictions.

2.3.2. RNN-based methods

RNN-based methods for instance segmentation use the sequential nature of recurrent neural networks to segment instances one at a time. These methods use attention mechanisms to iteratively focus on different regions of the image, allowing the model to handle occlusions and improve segmentation accuracy. The RNNs process each instance in sequence, allowing the model to produce detailed segmentation masks, while naturally handling variable-length outputs. The main models are described below.

End-to-End Instance Segmentation (ETE) [93] uses a recurrent neural network (RNN) with an attention mechanism to perform instance segmentation. The model is designed to mimic a human-like counting process by iteratively segmenting each object in the scene. The architecture consists of four main components: an external memory to track segmented objects, a box proposal network to locate objects, a segmentation network to segment pixels within the proposed boxes, and a scoring network to determine when to stop. The box-proposal network predicts bounding boxes using a CNN, while the segmentation network generates pixel-level masks for each object using deconvolution layers. The attention mechanism allows the model to iteratively focus on different regions of the image, handling occlusions, and improving segmentation accuracy.

The RNN for Semantic Instance Segmentation (RSIS) [94] model uses recurrent neural networks (RNNs) to sequentially generate binary masks and their associated class probabilities for each object in an image. This end-to-end trainable model eliminates the need for post-processing steps

typically required by object proposal-based methods. The architecture consists of an encoder-decoder network, where the encoder is a pre-trained ResNet-101 and the decoder is a hierarchical recurrent architecture using convolutional LSTMs. This allows RSIS to predict one instance at a time, naturally handling variable-length outputs. The model incorporates skip connections to exploit low-level features of the encoder, thus improving segmentation accuracy.

2.3.3. Self-attention

Self-attention mechanisms in instance segmentation use transformers to refine query boxes and mask predictions. These methods exploit the ability of transformers to focus on relevant image regions and handle long-range dependencies, thereby improving both detection and segmentation performance. The self-attention mechanism allows the model to integrate context from different parts of the image, resulting in more coherent and accurate segmentation masks. The main models are described below.

End-to-End Instance Segmentation with Transformers (ISTR) [95] is the first framework to integrate transformers for end-to-end instance segmentation. This model predicts low-dimensional mask embeddings instead of high-dimensional masks, allowing efficient training with fewer samples. ISTR employs a set prediction loss based on bipartite matching, eliminating the need for non-maximum suppression. The architecture incorporates a recurrent refinement strategy, enabling concurrent detection and segmentation.

The Mask2Former model [96] introduces a universal image segmentation architecture capable of addressing panoptic, instance, and semantic segmentation tasks. It employs a Transformer-based framework with masked attention, which restricts attention to localized features centered around predicted segments. The architecture consists of a backbone feature extractor, a pixel decoder, and a transformer decoder. Key innovations include multi-scale high-resolution features to handle small objects, and optimization improvements such as switching the order of self- and cross-attention, making query features learnable, and removing dropout. These improvements result in faster convergence and better performance.

Segmenting Objects by Learning Queries (SOLQ) [97] introduces an end-to-end framework for instance segmentation based on DETR [98]. SOLQ segments objects by learning unified queries, where each query represents an object with multiple attributes: class, location, and mask. These queries perform classification, box regression, and mask coding simultaneously. The mask vectors are supervised during training by compression coding of raw spatial masks and can be transformed back into spatial masks during inference. The architecture consists of a feature extraction network, a transformer decoder, and a unified query representation module.

3. Evaluation metrics

Instance segmentation is a computer vision task that involves detecting and delineating each distinct object of interest in an image. Unlike semantic segmentation, which assigns each pixel to a category without distinguishing between object instances, instance segmentation not only identifies the category of each object, but also distinguishes between different instances of the same category. Evaluating instance segmentation models requires a robust set of quality metrics that measure various aspects of performance, including accuracy, efficiency, and model complexity. These metrics provide a comprehensive evaluation that guides improvements and comparisons between different models. Table 4 shows a general summary of the quality metrics described in this section.

3.1. Preliminary terms

Intersection over the Union (IoU): The Intersection Over Unity (IOU) can be considered one of the basic starting metrics, as it is used for

Table 4
Summary of instance segmentation quality metrics.

Metric Category	Metric Name	Equation Reference	Application/Importance
Basic Metrics	Intersection over Union (IoU)	Eq. (1)	Used as a fundamental metric for more complex metrics, it quantifies overlap mask precision.
Threshold Metrics	Overlap Threshold (α)	Described in text	Adjusted based on application to balance precision and recall. Affects calculations of AP, mAP, and NMS.
Accuracy Metrics	Average Precision (AP)	Eqs. (2), (3)	Widely used in object detection and instance segmentation, useful for comparing models.
	Difference in Count (DiC)	Eq. (4)	Critical in applications needing precise instance counts like crowd counting.
	Symmetric Best Dice (SBD)	Eqs. (5), (6), (7)	Evaluates the accuracy of predicted instance shapes and overlaps. Useful for model segmentation capability assessment.
	Mean Coverage Loss	Eqs. (8), (9), (10)	Assesses overlap quality, highlighting the importance of accurately covering larger instances.
	Average Best Overlap (ABO)	Described in text	Measures alignment of best-predicted instances with ground-truth, indicating optimal model performance.
	AvgFP (Average False Positives)	Described in text	Helps to understand the tendency of the model to generate false alarms, important for precision-sensitive applications.
	AvgFn (Average False Negatives)	Described in text	Indicates model's tendency to miss actual instances, crucial for comprehensive detection in safety-critical applications.
Efficiency Metrics	Instance Precision (InsPr)	Described in text	Essential for applications that require high accuracy with fewer false positives.
	Instance Recall (InsRe)	Described in text	Important for ensuring no instances are missed, crucial for exhaustive instance detection.
	Instance F1 Score (InsF1)	Eq. (11)	Balances precision and recall, offering a comprehensive measure of model's predictive performance.
Efficiency Metrics	Inference Time	Described in text	Measures the speed of the model during the prediction phase, crucial for real-time applications such as autonomous driving.
Model Complexity Metrics	GFLOPs (Giga Floating-Point Operations Per Second)	Described in text	Quantifies computational complexity, which is important for evaluating deployment feasibility in various environments.

the calculation of other quality metrics. It is a metric inherited from detection systems. This metric quantifies how the two ROIs overlap, on the one hand, the ground truth (GT) and on the other hand the predicted one. Its value is bounded between 0 and 1 where zero means no overlap and 1 indicates total overlap.

$$\text{IoU} = \frac{\text{Area}_{\cap}}{\text{Area}_{\cup}} \quad (1)$$

In the context of masks, such as instance segmentation, it is also known as the Jaccard index [99] and corresponds to the number of pixels at the intersection of binary masks divided by the number of pixels at the union of the masks. Both metrics are equivalent in their mathematical definition, since both quantify the similarity between two sets by computing the ratio between their intersection and union.

Overlap Threshold: The overlap threshold, α also called IoU threshold value is a measure used to decide whether a predicted mask sufficiently matches a ground truth mask of an object. In other words, it allows the identification of correctly classified pixels true positives (TP) and true negatives (TN) and also wrongly classified pixels, false positives (FP), and false negatives (FN) for each of the classes and instance to be segmented. This is essential for the calculation of quality metrics such as Average Precision (AP), Mean Average Precision (mAP), Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS), precision, and recall. This implies that it has a direct impact on these metrics.

This threshold can be adjusted depending on the application and the desired balance between precision and recall. Higher thresholds (eg, 0.7) may result in fewer false positives, but may miss some true positives. Lower thresholds (e.g., 0.3) may capture more true positives but also increase false positives.

3.2. Accuracy metrics

Average Precision (AP) [5]: The AP is a widely used metric in object detection and instance segmentation. It measures the precision of the predicted instance masks at various overlap thresholds. This metric provides a balanced measure of both recall and precision, highlighting the model's ability to detect objects accurately across different overlap thresholds and instance sizes. It is a robust metric that can be used to compare different models on a standardized scale. The standard mean average precision metric is defined as follows:

$$AP(y, \hat{y}) = \frac{1}{N} \sum \text{area}(\text{PR}) \quad (2)$$

$$PR = \sum_a \sum_{\hat{y}_j} PR(y_i, \hat{y}_j) \cdot I[\text{IoU}(y_i, \hat{y}_j) > \alpha] \quad (3)$$

where N is the number of object classes, y and \hat{y} means the ground-truth and predictions instance masks respectively. PR is the smoother precision recall curve. Then, $\text{area}(\bullet)$ is the area function under smoother precision recall curve, $I(\bullet)$ is the indicator function, $\text{IoU}(\bullet)$ is the Intersection over Union and α is the overlap threshold. Finally, the j -predicted instance and the j GT instances. On the other hand, it is common to find metrics AP_{50} , AP_{75} and AP_{95} which show the average accuracy value at thresholds of 0.5, 0.75 and 0.95.

In terms of accuracy, AP is commonly used for different instance sizes. Thus, it is common to find AP_S , AP_M and AP_L designed to evaluate the average accuracy of small instances ($AP_S \rightarrow$ number of pixels less than 32^2), medium instances ($AP_M \rightarrow$ number of pixels between 32^2 and 96^2), and large instances ($AP_L \rightarrow$ number of pixels greater than 96^2) [5].

Difference in Count (DiC) [5]: DiC quantifies the counting accuracy of a model by measuring the difference between the number of predicted instances and the actual number of ground-truth instances.

The absolute value of the mean difference in counts is averaged across all images. This metric is particularly useful for applications where the exact number of instances is critical, such as crowd counting or inventory management.

$$DiC(y_c, \hat{y}_c) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N (\#y_{c,i} - \#\hat{y}_{c,i}) \quad (4)$$

For each i -th image in the total N , $\#y$ and \hat{y} denote the number of instances with class "c" in the ground truth and predicted by the \hat{y} model.

This metric is commonly found in absolute value as $|DiC|$ [5,100].

Symmetric Best Dice (SBD) [5]: SBD measures the similarity between predicted and ground-truth instance masks using the Dice score, which measures the degree of overlap between the predicted mask and ground truth as IoU.

$$\text{Dice}(\%) = \frac{2|y \cap \hat{y}|}{|y| + |\hat{y}|} \quad (5)$$

Where $| \cdot |$ is the numbers of pixels of the instance area of y and \hat{y} different instance sets, first ground truth and then predicted by the model

For each ground-truth label, the best predicted match label is found by maximizing the Dice coefficient (5). The best Dice (BD) is defined as (6). The scores are then averaged to produce the SBD.

$$BD(y^a, y^b) = \frac{1}{M} \sum_{i=1}^M \max_{1 \leq j \leq N} \frac{2|y_i^a \cap y_j^b|}{|y_i^a| + |y_j^b|} \quad (6)$$

y_i^a ($1 \leq i \leq M$) and y_j^b ($1 \leq j \leq N$) are two different instance subsets of instances segmented. The SBD between instance mask y (ground-truth) and predicted mask \hat{y} can be defined as (7).

$$SBD(y, \hat{y}) = \min(BD(\hat{y}, y), BD(y, \hat{y})) \quad (7)$$

This metric is useful for evaluating the accuracy of the predicted instance shapes and overlaps, providing information on the model's ability to accurately segment instances.

Mean Coverage Loss [5]: Mean weighted coverage loss (MWCov) and mean unweighted coverage loss (MUCov) are used for car segmentation using the KITTI [101] dataset in [93]. First, MWCov Weights these IoUs by the area of the ground truth masks. MUCov, Measures the maximum IoU of the ground truth with a predicted mask. MUCov averages the highest IoU for each ground-truth instance across all images. MWCov additionally weights these IoUs by instance area. These metrics assess the overlap quality between the predicted and ground-truth masks, emphasizing the importance of covering larger instances more accurately.

$$MWCov(y, \hat{y}) = \sum_i \beta \max_j(y_j, \hat{y}_j) \quad (8)$$

$$\beta = \frac{|y_i|}{\sum_i |y_i|} \quad (9)$$

$$MUCov(y, \hat{y}) = \sum_i \frac{1}{N} \max_j(y_j, \hat{y}_j) \quad (10)$$

Others [5]: In addition to the aforementioned metrics, there are still some useful metrics to evaluate an instance segmentation method. One such metric is the Average Best Overlap (ABO), which calculates the Jaccard index (IoU) between the best proposal for each ground-truth instance and the actual ground-truth instance. For each ground-truth instance, the highest IoU with any predicted instance is selected and averaged across all instances. The Average Best Overlap (ABO) metric provides a measure of the degree to which the best predicted instances align with the ground-truth instances, thereby highlighting the optimal performance of the model.

The **Average False Positives (AvgFP) [102]** metric quantifies the number of false positive instances per image, where the predicted instances do not overlap with any ground-truth instances. The average number of false positives is computed across all images. This metric helps to understand the propensity of the model to generate false alarms, which is crucial for applications where false positives can lead to significant issues. In contrast to AvgFP, the Average False Negatives (AvgFn) metric measures the number of false negative instances per image, where ground-truth instances do not overlap with any predicted instances. The average number of false negatives is computed across all images. This metric indicates the model's tendency to fail to identify

actual instances, which is of critical importance in safety-critical applications such as autonomous driving.

To further evaluate the precision of instance segmentation, the **Instance Precision** (*InsPr*) metric is used. *InsPr* quantifies precision by calculating the ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total number of predicted instances. It is defined as the quotient of the number of true positive instance predictions divided by the total number of predictions. High instance precision indicates fewer false positives, which is essential for applications that require high accuracy.

Similarly, the Instance Recall (*InsRe*) metric measures the recall of the instance segmentation by calculating the ratio of correctly predicted instances to the total number of ground-truth instances. *InsRe* is defined as the quotient of the number of true positive instance predictions divided by the total number of ground truth instances. A high instance recall indicates fewer missed instances, which is important for comprehensive detection.

Finally, the **Instance F1 Score** (*InsF1*) is used to balance precision and recall. The Instance F1 Score (*InsF1*) is the harmonic mean of instance precision and instance recall. In (11) it is shown how to calculate it.

$$InsF1 = 2 \cdot \frac{InsPr \cdot InsRe}{InsPr + InsRe} \quad (11)$$

This metric provides a single measure that reflects both the accuracy and completeness of the model's predictions, providing a balanced view of the model's performance.

3.3. Efficiency metrics

The inference time measures the speed of the model during the prediction phase, typically expressed in frames per second (FPS). It is also commonly found on other time scales, such as milliseconds (ms) [103]. This metric is essential for real-time applications where fast decisions must be made, such as autonomous vehicles or real-time video analysis. It is a hardware-dependent metric and is therefore often combined with model complexity metrics such as FLOPs (Floating-Point Operations Per Second) to draw conclusions.

3.4. Model complexity metrics

The FLOPs (Floating-Point Operations Per Second) metric quantifies the computational complexity of a model by measuring the number of floating-point operations performed per second. It is commonly found in orders of billions ("gigas"), which is why it is known as GFLOPs, which means the number of floating-point operations performed per second in billions. This metric provides a clear indication of the processing power required to run the model, especially during intensive tasks such as training and inference. GFLOPs is a critical metric for evaluating the efficiency and feasibility of deploying a model in a variety of environments, from high-end servers to resource-constrained devices [42]. It is often used in conjunction with hardware-dependent metrics such as inference time to provide a comprehensive view of a model's performance and its practical deployment implications.

4. Datasets challenges

The main instance segmentation techniques are based on supervised learning models, which require massive datasets. Labeling datasets for the instance segmentation task implies a large effort for the annotators compared to bounds box annotation or semantic segmentation. As shown in [104] fine labeling at the pixel level involves a 1.5 h per image, while a labeling with bounding boxes is 15 times less. The same is true for emerging datasets such as the one proposed by L. Hösch [105] for inland waterway transport.

Recently, with the arrival of foundational image segmentation models such as SAM (Segment Anything Model) [106] and its different

versions [107–109], the instance labeling work is living a revolution. This semi-supervised segmentation technology can segment any object using an input such as a bounding box, another mask, or even text. In this way, datasets manually labeled by experts with bounding boxes can be extended into datasets for instance segmentation. Also, current zero-shot learning paradigms allow for massive dataset generation or at least pre-labeling to facilitate the supervision of expert annotators.

Regarding the definition of masks in instance segmentation, there are two widespread forms in the literature, polygons and in Run-Length Encoder (RLE) coding. Polygons outline regions by specifying the vertices of the shape. This method provides a precise and flexible delineation of complex shapes, but requires more manual effort and memory. It is ideal for detailed annotation tasks such as medical or aerial imaging amongst others. RLE compresses mask data by encoding successive pixels with the same value as a single data value and count. This method is memory efficient, especially for large images with contiguous regions, but less accurate for complex shapes. It is often used in large datasets. Regardless of how the instances are defined, this process is generally completed by constructing masks of the image size where the instances are located as a binarized mask where all pixels of the image background have value 0 while the regions where the instances are located have value 1.

Given the effort involved in creating a structured database with annotations, the authors, together with the publication of the associated study, usually propose challenges to the scientific community.

The subsections in this section describe various datasets categorized as generalist, urban environment, or autonomous driving, context of drones and aerial imagery, video segmentation, and other datasets.

4.1. Generalist datasets for instance segmentation

This section covers key generalist datasets that represent the state of the art for developing new instance segmentation models. These datasets provide comprehensive and diverse annotations across different object classes, enabling robust model training and benchmarking. By leveraging these datasets, researchers and practitioners can advance the state of the art in instance segmentation, address real-world challenges, and ensure that their models perform well in diverse scenarios. Finally, Table 5 provides a summary of the datasets.

Microsoft Common Objects in Context (COCO) [6,110] dataset is a large-scale dataset for image classification, object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation. Additionally, it contains annotations for other challenges such as keypoints, stuff, panoptic and Captions. It contains 2.5 million labeled instances in 328,000 images and 91 object classes, with 80 of them used for instance segmentation. The images of COCO are captured from daily life scenes with different resolutions. Because of the large scale of this dataset, it has gradually become a widely used benchmark for instance segmentation competitions and model evaluation. Up to now, the COCO dataset has had two popular versions: COCO 2014 and COCO 2017. The difference between these two versions is the division of the dataset. COCO 2014 provides more than 83,000 images for training, 41,000 images for validation and 41,000 images for testing, while COCO 2017 has 118,000 training images, 5000 validation images and 41,000 testing images.

The Pascal Visual Object Classes (VOC) [111] dataset is a widely

Table 5
Generalist Datasets for Instance Segmentation.

Dataset	Instances	Classes	Reference
Microsoft COCO	2.5 million instances	91 object classes (80 for instance segmentation)	[6,110]
Pascal VOC	20,000 images	20 object categories	[111]
LVIS	2 million instances	1000 + object categories	[112]
Open Images	9 million images	600 object classes	[113, 114]

used benchmark for object detection, classification, and segmentation tasks. It contains more than 20,000 images with annotations for 20 object categories. The dataset includes pixel-wise segmentations, bounding boxes, and object class labels. VOC challenges have been held annually since 2005, promoting advancements in object recognition and segmentation. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets, providing a comprehensive resource for developing and evaluating computer vision algorithms.

The Large Vocabulary Instance Segmentation (LVIS) [112] dataset is a large-scale dataset for instance segmentation. It contains more than 2 million high-quality instance annotations for more than 1000 object categories. The images in LVIS are sourced from the COCO dataset, but with more detailed and extensive annotations. LVIS emphasizes long-tail object categories, providing a challenging benchmark for models to recognize and segment rare objects. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets, making it a valuable resource for instance segmentation research.

The Open Images dataset [113,114]: The Open Images dataset is a large-scale dataset for object detection, instance segmentation, and visual relationship detection. It contains approximately 9 million images with annotations for 600 object classes. The dataset includes more than 15 million bounding boxes, 375,000 segmentation masks, and 30 million image-level labels. Open Images features a diverse range of scenes and objects, making it a comprehensive benchmark for various computer vision tasks. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets, providing a robust resource for the development and evaluation of models.

4.2. Urban or autonomous driving datasets

Instance segmentation in urban and autonomous driving scenarios is a critical task for developing robust computer vision models. This review highlights key datasets that provide essential resources for instance segmentation, including Cityscapes [115], KITTI [116], Mapillary Vistas [117], KITTI InstanceMotSeg [118], A2D2 [119], ApolloScape [120] and (BDD100K) [121]. These datasets cover diverse urban environments and complex traffic scenes, supporting tasks such as semantic segmentation, object detection, and motion segmentation, and are invaluable for advancing research and development in autonomous driving technologies. Table 6 provides a summary of the databases.

The Cityscapes dataset [115] is a large-scale dataset designed for understanding urban scenes, specifically for semantic segmentation, instance segmentation, and object detection tasks. It contains 5,000 high-quality annotated images collected from 50 different cities, with annotations for 30 object classes, including cars, pedestrians, and street signs. The dataset also includes 20,000 weakly annotated images.

Table 6
Urban or Autonomous Driving Datasets.

Dataset	Instances	Classes	Reference
Cityscapes	5 K annotated images	30 classes (cars, pedestrians, street signs, etc.)	[115]
KITTI	15 K+ images	80 classes (cars, pedestrians, cyclists, etc.)	[116]
MVD	25 K+ high-res images	66 classes (vehicles, pedestrians, vegetation, etc.)	[117]
KITTI IMS	12.9 K annotated samples	Dynamic objects (cars, pedestrians, bicycles, trucks, vans)	[118]
A2D2	41,277 frames	Various classes (vehicles, pedestrians, traffic signs, etc.)	[119]
ApolloScape	143,906 frames	Various classes (cars, pedestrians, bicycles, road infrastructure, etc.)	[120]
BDD100K	100 K driving videos	Various tasks (scene tagging, object bounding box, lane marking, drivable area, instance segmentation)	[121]

Cityscapes represents diverse urban environments with varying weather conditions, times of day, and complex traffic scenes, making it a comprehensive benchmark for developing and evaluating computer vision models in urban contexts. The dataset is divided into training, validation, and test sets.

Karlsruhe Institute of Technology and Toyota Technological Institute (KITTI) [116] is a large-scale dataset created to advance autonomous driving research. It addresses a wide range of tasks, including object detection, object tracking, instance segmentation, and road scene understanding. The dataset contains over 15,000 images with annotations for 80 object classes, captured using vehicle-mounted stereo cameras. KITTI features challenging real-world scenarios with varying lighting conditions, moving objects, and cluttered backgrounds, providing a solid benchmark for developing autonomous driving models. The dataset is divided into training and test sets to facilitate model development and evaluation.

The Mapillary Vistas Dataset (MVD) [117] is a large-scale, diverse dataset for semantic segmentation and instance segmentation, focusing on street-level imagery. It contains more than 25000 high-resolution images collected from various parts of the world, annotated with pixel-accurate masks for 66 object classes. The dataset features a wide range of scenes, including different weather conditions, urban and rural environments, and various types of objects such as vehicles, pedestrians, and vegetation. MVD is divided into training, validation, and test sets, providing a comprehensive resource for developing and benchmarking computer vision models for street-level scene understanding.

The KITTI InstanceMotSeg dataset [118] is a specialized dataset designed for instance motion segmentation in the context of autonomous driving. It consists of 12.9 K annotated samples and improves on the previous KITTIMoSeg dataset. The dataset includes pixel-level instance masks for dynamic objects such as cars, pedestrians, bicycles, trucks, and vans across 1600 video snippets with over 8000 frames. KITTI InstanceMotSeg features challenging scenarios with complex motion patterns, varying illumination, and occlusions, making it a comprehensive benchmark for developing and evaluating models focused on motion segmentation. The dataset is divided into training (80 %) and test (20 %) sets, providing a robust resource for the advancement of autonomous driving technologies. The dataset supports both class-agnostic and semantic instance segmentation tasks, facilitating the development of models that can detect unseen objects based on their motion cues.

Audi Autonomous Driving Dataset (A2D2) [119] is a comprehensive dataset that includes images and 3D point clouds with annotations for 3D bounding boxes, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation. The dataset contains 41,277 frames with semantic segmentation labels and 12,497 frames with 3D bounding box annotations. It provides full 360-degree coverage using a suite of six cameras and five LiDAR units, facilitating robust autonomous driving research and model development.

ApolloScape Dataset [120] is a large-scale dataset for autonomous driving, offering 2D and 3D pixel-level segmentation, lane marking, instance segmentation, and depth information. It consists of 143,906 frames with 89,430 objects, covering various classes such as cars, pedestrians, bicycles, and road infrastructure. This dataset is valuable for developing models that require a comprehensive understanding of the scene and object detection in various driving environments.

The Berkeley DeepDrive 100 K (BDD100K) [121], part of the largest driving video dataset for heterogeneous multitask learning, provides a comprehensive evaluation platform for image recognition algorithms in autonomous driving. It contains 100,000 different driving videos with annotations for 10 tasks, such as scene tagging, object-bounding box, lane marking, drivable area, and instance segmentation. BDD100K captures a variety of driving scenarios in different weather conditions, times of day, and locations, improving the robustness of the model. This dataset is essential to advance research in understanding the road scene and provides unparalleled diversity and complexity for evaluating

algorithms in autonomous driving.

4.3. Drones and aerial imagery context

Instance segmentation in the context of drones and aerial imagery is an evolving field with unique challenges and opportunities. Unlike detection or semantic segmentation [122–124], which have been extensively researched, instance segmentation requires more detailed annotation and advanced modeling techniques. This section reviews key datasets that support instance segmentation tasks in aerial imagery and highlights their contributions to advancing computer vision research in traffic monitoring, environmental analysis, and maritime surveillance. Table 7 provides a summary of the databases.

Drone Traffic Instance Segmentation Dataset [125] comprises 1332 images of traffic scenes captured by drones. It includes instance segmentation annotations for various traffic vehicles as bicycle, bus car, and lorry, making it useful for traffic monitoring and management applications. This dataset supports the development of models to improve traffic analysis through drone imagery.

Busy parking Lot Dataset [126] is designed for vehicle detection and instance segmentation in UAV-captured videos of busy parking lots. It includes 20,000 annotated frames showing vehicles in various orientations and states of occlusion. The dataset supports the development of models for traffic monitoring and management, providing a real-world benchmark for instance segmentation tasks in dynamic parking lot environments.

Drone_Bird_Aircraft Instance Segmentation Dataset [127] contains 4470 images annotated for example segmentation, focusing on objects such as drones, birds, and airplanes. It is designed to facilitate the development of models for detecting and segmenting these objects in aerial imagery. The dataset contains diverse scenes and provides a robust resource for training and evaluating instance segmentation algorithms.

Instance Segmentation in Aerial Images Dataset (iSAID) [128] is a large-scale dataset created for instance segmentation in aerial images. It includes 655,451 object instances across 2806 high-resolution images, annotated for 15 categories such as planes, ships, storage tanks, and vehicles. The dataset addresses unique challenges posed by aerial imagery, including a high number of instances per image, large object-scale variations, and the presence of numerous small objects. iSAID is designed to ensure precise localization with per-pixel annotations, making it an essential resource for detailed scene analysis in aerial imagery. It serves as a benchmark for instance segmentation tasks, facilitating the development and evaluation of specialized solutions for aerial image analysis.

VHR-10 Dataset COCO [129,130] is a challenging ten-class geo-object detection dataset designed for very high resolution (VHR) optical remote sensing. It contains a total of 800 images, with 715 color images acquired from Google Earth at spatial resolutions ranging from 0.5 to 2 m, and 85 pansharpened color infrared images from the Vaihingen dataset at a spatial resolution of 0.08 m. The dataset is divided into two

sets: a positive image set containing 650 images with at least one target, and a negative image set containing 150 images without targets. In the positive image set, 757 airplanes, 302 ships, 655 storage tanks, 390 baseball diamonds, 524 tennis courts, 159 basketball courts, 163 athletic fields, 224 harbors, 124 bridges, and 477 vehicles are manually annotated with bounding boxes and instance masks, providing ground truth for instance segmentation tasks. This dataset supports the development and evaluation of models that require precise object detection and instance segmentation in high-resolution aerial imagery.

UOW-Vessel [131] dataset is a comprehensive benchmark for vessel detection and segmentation using high-resolution optical satellite images. It comprises 3500 images sourced from 14 countries on four continents, featuring 35,598 instances in 10 categories of vessels. Unlike other datasets that offer only bounding-box annotations, UOW-Vessel provides precise polygon annotations, capturing intricate vessel details and accounting for occlusions and varying orientations. This dataset supports various tasks including object detection, semantic segmentation, and instance segmentation, offering a valuable resource for advancing deep learning methods in maritime surveillance and vessel recognition.

SAR Ship Detection Dataset (SSDD) [132] is designed for ship detection and segmentation using synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery. It contains a large number of annotated images representing different types of ships in different sea states. The dataset provides 116,491 SAR images with annotations for both detection and instance segmentation tasks. SSDD is valuable for maritime surveillance and monitoring and supports the development of robust models capable of operating in challenging marine environments.

High Resolution SAR Images Dataset (HRSID) [133] is developed for ship detection and instance segmentation using synthetic aperture radar (SAR) imagery. It includes 5604 images cropped to 800 × 800 pixels from 136 panoramic SAR imageries, featuring 16,951 annotated ships. The dataset covers various imaging conditions and resolutions from 1 m to 5 m. Ships are annotated with polygons transformed into the MS COCO format, supporting both object detection and instance segmentation tasks. HRSID is divided into training sets (65 %) and test sets (35 %) sets and evaluated using state-of-the-art detectors to establish baseline performance for maritime surveillance applications.

S2-SHIPS [134] dataset is designed for ship detection in Sentinel-2 multi-spectral images, enhancing awareness of the maritime domain for security and economic monitoring. It includes 16 high-resolution images, each covering 167 square kilometers, with a total of 1053 ships annotated at the pixel level. These images, captured in various harbor and coastal regions, provide data on both moored and moving ships. The dataset, with a resolution of 10 m and an image size of 1783 × 938 pixels, supports precise ship detection and instance segmentation tasks. It features diverse weather conditions, making it robust for various environmental settings and advancing maritime surveillance technology.

Airbus Oil-Storage Tank Instance Segmentation [135] dataset contains 98 SPOT image extracts at approximately 1.2 m resolution, each

Table 7
Instance segmentation in the context of drones and aerial imagery.

Type	Dataset	Instances	Classes	Reference
Drones	Drone Traffic Instance Segmentation	1332 images	Traffic vehicles (bicycle, bus, car, lorry)	[125]
	Busy Parking Lot Dataset	20,000 frames	Vehicles in various orientations and states of occlusion.	[126]
	Drone_Bird_Aircraft Instance Segmentation	4470 images	Drones, birds, and airplanes	[127]
Aerial Imagery	iSAID	655,451 objects	15 categories (planes, ships, storage tanks, vehicles, etc.)	[128]
	VHR-10 Dataset COCO	800 images	10 classes (airplanes, ships, storage tanks, baseball diamonds, etc.)	[129,130]
	UOW-Vessel	35,598 instances	10 categories of vessels	[131]
	SSDD	116,491 images	Ships in different sea states	[132]
	HRSID	16,951 ships	Ships	[133]
	S2-SHIPS	1053 ships	Ships	[134]
	Airbus Oil-Storage Tank Instance Segmentation	98 images	Oil storage tanks	[135]
	BUCEA 2.0	1400 images	Building rooftops with various geometric and spectral features	[136]

stored as a 2560 × 2560 pixel JPEG file, covering 3 kilometers on the ground. These globally selected images include precise polygon annotations for oil storage tanks, detailed in a CSV file. The dataset supports object detection and instance segmentation tasks and includes five additional unannotated images for model testing. This dataset is intended to support the development of models for geospatial analysis using high-resolution satellite imagery.

BUCEA 2.0 Dataset [136] is a self-annotated collection designed for the delineation and extraction of building rooftops, including different building styles from different geographic regions. It combines public building datasets such as the WHU Building Dataset [137], the INRIA Aerial Image Dataset [138], and the Massachusetts Building Dataset [139,140], resulting in a comprehensive dataset spanning different sensors, resolutions, cities, and scenes. The BUCEA 2.0 dataset includes high-resolution remote sensing images from six typical areas in China, reflecting diverse building styles influenced by regional climate and environmental conditions. It builds on BUCEA 1.0 [141], guided by Tupu theory and geographic knowledge, to enhance geographic coupling and generalizability of models. The dataset comprises 1400 images, with 800 images of 512 × 512 pixels and 600 images of the same size. These images are annotated using Labelme, with geometric shapes and spectral characteristics classified and transformed into the COCO dataset format. Geometric features include various shapes such as rectangles, circles, and complex combinations, while spectral characteristics are categorized by visual colors like red, yellow, green, blue, and various shades of gray and brown. This dataset supports precise building rooftop instance segmentation tasks by providing detailed geometric and spectral features, accounting for geographic heterogeneity and coupling.

4.4. Generalist datasets for video instance segmentation

Although video instance segmentation is a different area of research, its close relationship with static image instance segmentation can be seen as an opportunity for future applications. This section therefore reviews the main datasets that support video instance segmentation, providing the reader with new resources to advance research in dynamic and occlusion-rich environments. Table 8 provides a summary of the databases.

The Densely Annotated Video Segmentation (DAVIS) [142] dataset is a benchmark designed for video object segmentation tasks. It comprises high-quality video sequences with detailed pixel-level annotations. The dataset features a diverse set of videos with various object classes and

Table 8
Generalist Datasets for Video Instance Segmentation.

Dataset	Instances	Classes	Reference
DAVIS	High-quality video sequences	Various object classes including humans, animals, vehicles, and objects	[142]
OVIS	296,000 instance masks	25 object categories such as people, vehicles, animals, and sports equipment	[45]
VS100	100 high-resolution videos	Different scenes including humans, vehicles, animals, and natural elements	[143, 144]
ADE20K	20,000 images	150 object categories, including buildings, vehicles, people, animals, and furniture.	[145]
UVO	Various videos	Different object appearances and motions, including everyday objects and dynamic scenes	[146]
YouTube-VIS	2883 video clips	40 object categories that include people, animals, vehicles, and household objects	[7]
TAO	2900 videos	Wide range of categories including people, animals, vehicles, and objects	[147]

challenging scenarios, such as occlusions and fast object motions, making it a valuable resource for developing and evaluating video instance segmentation models.

Occluded Video Instance Segmentation (OVIS) [45] is a large dataset specifically designed to address occlusion challenges in video instance segmentation. It contains 296,000 high-quality instance masks in 901 videos in 25 object categories. Videos in OVIS contain complex scenes with frequent and severe occlusions, providing a valuable benchmark for evaluating the robustness of models in handling occluded instances.

Video Segmentation Benchmark 100 (VSB100) [143,144] is a dataset focused on evaluating video object segmentation algorithms. It consists of 100 high-resolution videos with densely annotated frames covering different scenes and object classes. VSB100 provides a standardized benchmark for comparing the performance of different segmentation models in terms of accuracy and computational efficiency.

ADE20K [145] is a comprehensive semantic segmentation dataset that contains more than 20,000 images annotated with pixel-level labels for 150 object categories. While primarily used for semantic segmentation, ADE20K's detailed annotations make it a valuable resource for developing and benchmarking instance segmentation models.

Unidentified Video Objects (UVO) [146] is a dataset aimed at recognizing and segmenting previously unseen objects in videos. It contains a wide variety of videos with different object appearances and motions, providing a challenging benchmark for developing models that can generalize to new and unknown objects in dynamic environments.

YouTube Video Instance Segmentation (YouTube-VIS) [7] is a large-scale dataset for video instance segmentation. It consists of 2883 high-resolution YouTube video clips annotated with instance masks for 40 object categories. The dataset captures a wide range of real-world scenarios, including complex backgrounds, varying lighting conditions, and object interactions, making it an essential resource for advancing video instance segmentation research.

Tracking Any Object (TAO) [147] is a dataset designed to track objects in videos, covering a wide range of categories and scenes. It includes over 2900 videos with dense instance annotations, supporting the development of models that can track objects consistently across different frames and handle challenging conditions such as occlusions and rapid movements.

4.5. Other datasets

There are a variety of challenges that instance segmentation can address. In the following section, we describe three datasets that exemplify such diversity. These examples address the problem of segmenting instances from urban trees, supermarket products, and multi object tracking. Table 9 provides a summary of the databases.

The Urban Street Tree Dataset [148] is designed for image classification and instance segmentation of urban street trees, providing 41,467 high-resolution images (22,872 annotated) of 50 tree species from 10 urban scenes. It includes subdatasets for leaves, stems, branches, flowers, and fruits, captured under different lighting, seasonal, and shooting conditions. The annotations are fine-grained, using polygons to outline individual objects. This dataset supports tasks such as the

Table 9
Other datasets.

Dataset	Instances	Classes	Reference
Urban Street Tree Dataset	41,467 images	50 tree species, including leaves, stems, branches, flowers, and fruits	[148]
Densely Segmented Supermarket (D2S)	21,000 images	60 object classes such as fruits, vegetables, and packaged goods	[149]
Multi-Object Tracking and Segmentation (MOTS)	65,213 pixel masks	977 objects including cars and pedestrians	[150]

identification of tree species and instance segmentation, aiding urban forest management, environmental monitoring, and public understanding of urban biodiversity.

The Densely Segmented Supermarket (D2S) [149] dataset targets real-world applications in automated checkout, inventory and warehouse systems. It contains 21,000 images of 700 scenes with varying levels of background, clutter, and occlusion. Each scene was photographed ten times under three different lighting conditions using a high-resolution industrial color camera mounted on an off-center turntable. The dataset contains 60 hierarchically organized object classes, such as fruits, vegetables, and packaged goods.

The Multi-Object Tracking and Segmentation (MOTS) [150] dataset extends the task of multi-object tracking to include pixel-level instance segmentation. This dataset provides dense annotations for 65,213 pixel masks over 977 different objects (cars and pedestrians) in 10,870 video frames, derived from the KITTI and MOTChallenge datasets. The annotations were created using a semi-automatic process that augmented existing bounding-box annotations with detailed segmentation masks.

5. Discussion

Instance segmentation aims to identify each object instance within an image and delineate its precise boundaries. This capability is critical for a variety of applications, including autonomous driving, medical imaging, industrial automation, and environmental monitoring. The ability to accurately segment instances enables a detailed understanding of complex scenes, facilitating advanced analysis and decision-making.

One of the major challenges in instance segmentation is dealing with variations in viewpoint, occlusions, lighting conditions, and the presence of small or densely packed objects. These challenges require the development of robust methods that can generalize across different scenarios. The main methodological approaches to instance segmentation include two-stage, single-stage, and multi-stage methods. Two-stage methods, such as Mask R-CNN, involve region proposal generation followed by mask prediction, which typically provides high accuracy at the cost of increased computational complexity. In contrast, single-stage methods perform detection and segmentation in a single pass, increasing efficiency and speed, making them suitable for real-time applications. Multi-stage methods refine predictions incrementally, using information from each stage to progressively improve accuracy. However, single-stage methods often struggle with small object detection and occluded scenes due to their streamlined architectures, while multi-stage methods can suffer from increased latency, which limits their use in real-time applications.

Evaluating the performance of instance segmentation models requires comprehensive metrics that assess different aspects of model performance. Common metrics include Average Precision (AP), which balances precision and recall across different overlap thresholds, and Intersection over Union (IoU), which measures the overlap between predicted and ground truth masks. Additional metrics such as Difference in Count (DiC) and Symmetric Best Dice (SBD) provide insight into the counting accuracy and quality of predicted instance shapes, respectively. But metrics like IoU can oversimplify complex scenarios by considering only spatial overlap, ignoring shape accuracy or occlusion effects. Furthermore, metrics such as DiC and SBD, although informative, are not used consistently across datasets, making cross-model comparisons difficult.

The development and benchmarking of instance segmentation models rely heavily on large and diverse datasets. Generalist datasets, such as COCO and LVIS, provide rich annotations across numerous object categories, supporting robust model training and evaluation. Specialized datasets such as Cityscapes and KITTI focus on urban environments and autonomous driving scenarios, addressing specific challenges such as varying lighting conditions and dynamic object interactions. However, these datasets often have biases, such as a dominance of urban or daytime scenarios, which can hinder model

generalization to other environments, such as rural or nighttime. Other datasets address unique challenges in drone and aerial imagery or video instance segmentation, highlighting the need for accurate and context-aware models in these domains. Drone and aerial imagery data sets, such as iSAID and VHR-10, are crucial because they offer unique perspectives and challenges, such as varying altitudes and complex backgrounds, essential for applications in traffic monitoring, environmental analysis, and maritime surveillance. Unfortunately, creating such datasets requires extensive manual effort to fine-grained annotation, which increases costs and limits their size and variability.

In summary, instance segmentation is a key technology with broad applications. The field has seen significant methodological advances, with different approaches addressing different performance and efficiency requirements. Addressing challenges such as occlusion, small object detection, and varying lighting conditions remains critical, with advanced techniques showing promise in overcoming these hurdles. Robust evaluation metrics are essential for a comprehensive assessment of model performance, guiding improvements and comparisons. Large, diverse datasets are critical for training and evaluating models to ensure that they are well-rounded and capable of handling real-world complexities. However, researchers and practitioners must remain aware of the limitations of the datasets, such as representational biases and annotation challenges, which may affect the applicability of the model. Future research should focus on improving the robustness of the model, real-time performance, and the ability to generalize across diverse and complex environments. The integration of semi-supervised and unsupervised learning methods can reduce the reliance on large labeled datasets, further advancing the field. By addressing these issues, instance segmentation can continue to evolve, providing increasingly sophisticated tools and technologies for a wide range of applications.

Author contributions

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Molina José Manuel: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Llerena Juan Pedro:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Usero Luis:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Patricio Miguel Angel:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Software,

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Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data Availability

No data was used for the research described in the article.

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